

Evaluating the Effectiveness of the CPTD Programmes Delivered by the Zululand Education District to Improve Teacher Performance

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 07, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: February 08, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Teacher Development, Continuous, Andragogy, Quality Education, Traditional And Collaborative Approaches</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7618713</p>	<p><i>Currently, every country around the globe is undergoing extensive reforms to improve the quality of its educational systems. The best method of improving the quality of education is instituting continuous professional teacher development (CPTD) programmes. Thus, the study reports on an investigation of the perception and experiences of teachers about delivering effective CPTD programmes in the Zululand district. Qualitative one-on-one interviews with teachers, principals from both primary and secondary schools and district officials as well as a document study were conducted. Focus group interviews were also conducted to complement the one-on-one interviews. The study found that CPTD programmes are poorly implemented in the Zululand district since traditional methods such as lecture and cascade methods of delivery are employed. The study recommends the district establish a rigorous mechanism to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of the CPTD programmes before, during and after the implementation process. It also recommends the district improve the consultation process, teachers need to be consulted when drawing policies so that they own and embrace them. The study also recommends that the district use interactive, collaborative methods to implement the CPTD programmes. CPTD programmes must address the needs of teachers and schools, not the other way around. District officials must be trained in Andragogy theory for effective facilitation.</i></p>

Introduction

Currently, every country around the globe is undergoing extensive reforms to improve the quality of its educational systems. A proper education system provides quality education and knowledge to the customer (Rastogi & Kumar, 2016). Several research studies conducted in South Africa indicate that the country's education system is consistently underperforming. This was demonstrated by the underperformance of South African learners in comparison to those of other countries. The poor performance of South African learners indicates a problem with the performance of their teachers. Most research revealed the quality of a teacher as one of the most important factors affecting student achievements (Spaull, 2013). Thus, there is a great need for the South African Department of Education to urgently forge programmes which would improve teachers' performance. The best technique for improving the quality of teachers is professional teacher development programmes (Kinser-Traut, & Marx, 2022). For Professional Development (PD) to be effective and sustainable, it must be delivered continuously (Van der Merwe-Muller & Dasoo, 2021). Consequently, it is referred to as Continuous Professional Teacher Development (CPTD) programme. Although CPTD programmes are not a panacea for all education development initiatives, they do play an important role in the development of teacher performance (Chigonga & Mutodi, 2019). Teachers learn, learn how to learn, and enhance their knowledge through CPTD programmes to improve their students' performance (Avalos, 2011). Thus, CPTD programmes are designed to assist teachers in coping with and implementing all-new programmes aimed at enhancing their performance and thereby increasing the quality of an education system. Darling-Hammond, Hyler & Gardner (2017) propose that teachers require ample time for CPTD programmes to study, practice, apply, and reflect on new tactics that will enable them to make improvements in their practice. Many educational improvement projects have failed to achieve their intended aims because teachers have not received appropriate professional development programmes (Darling-Hammond, et al., 2017). As a result, the purpose of this study is to find out whether professional development programmes (PDP) offered to teachers in South Africa were effective in helping them enhance their students' performance. The Department of Education has District offices, whose primary purpose is to deliver the CPTD programmes to schools to enhance the performance of both teachers and learners (Swennen, 2018). Patton, Parker & Tannehill, (2015) contend that CPTD programmes to have an impact on the performance of teachers, need to be directed, sustained, and advocated by leadership in the district. The ongoing underperformance of students in the Zululand district warrants an investigation into

whether the district offices are providing teachers with effective CPTD programmes to assist them in improving student performance.

Literature review

School systems around the world require their teachers to participate in CPTD programmes, which are designed to keep them up to date on current education advancements (Darling-Hammond, et al., 2017). A teacher is at the core of any classroom instruction, which is regarded as the heart of an education system because most educational activities are based in the classroom. The quality of an education system is then determined by what is happening in the classroom, which is where there is an interaction between the learner, the teacher, and the curriculum. Teachers are the most prominent components who directly affect the quality of education because they are directly responsible for the quality of instructions imparted to learners in the classroom (Sahu, 2016). Sayed & Badroodien, (2016) postulate that the level of development of an education system is determined by the quality of its teachers. Therefore, the starting point when one wants to improve the quality of an education system is the improvement of teachers' techniques and strategies. Qablan et al., (2015) advocate that the quality of teaching cannot be developed without developing the quality of teachers. It is then the responsibility of an education system to develop teachers' skills, and their content knowledge and to provide them with the latest developments in the profession so that they can improve learner achievement. CPTD programmes have been proven to produce effective teachers for the improvement of learner achievement (Darling-Hammond, et al., 2017). According to SACE, like all professionals, teachers need to grow their knowledge and skills throughout their careers. Furthermore, CPTD opportunities help teachers to renew their commitment to the profession and their pride in the ideals of the profession (Mchunu, 2014). While Spaul, (2013) points out that if the capabilities of teachers are increased, their commitment increases. Sahu, (2016) avers that correct implementation and management of professional development opportunities will determine the quality of teachers and the level of their performance. Bayar (2014) cautions that CPTD programmes come in different forms and magnitudes and therefore they differ in strategy and emphasis whereas Sahu, (2016) warned that not every form of CPTD programme, even those with the greatest evidence of positive impact, is relevant to all teachers. It is therefore becoming crucial to describe the two major approaches used by CPTD programmes because the approaches to a CPTD programme determine its success. The two approaches which are usually employed in the delivery of CPTD programmes are namely, the traditional and collaborative approaches (Ono & Ferreira, 2010). The traditional approach refers to those CPTD programmes offered as short courses, seminars, and one-session workshops. Ono and Ferreira (2010) pointed out that workshops, conferences, and courses which are associated with the traditional PD programmes are usually lacking in relevance to the day-to-day teacher class requirements. There is no collaboration amongst teachers; in that way, they do not affect the teachers' performance. At the same time, Maistry (2008) maintains that the traditional approaches are not useful as they do not improve the teachers' content knowledge and their teaching skills. In addition, Steyn (2009) notes that the traditional approaches assume that various CPTD programmes employed, like lectures presented by experts, automatically result in the enhancement of teachers' knowledge and skills. In contrast Darling-Hammond, et al., (2017) posit that very little learning takes place in this approach. Similarly, in the traditional approach, teachers find themselves in sit-and-listen situations with minimal activities. This system is also referred to as the sit-and-get approach. The disadvantage of the traditional approach is that teachers will only benefit as individuals, causing teachers to have different approaches to a similar problem, which results in a situation where there is no ripple effect of the solutions in the schooling system (Nishimura, 2014). A collaborative approach is characterised by collaboration amongst teachers, and it occurs over an extended period (Maistry, 2008). In the same vein, Steyn (2014) observed that the content used during these programmes is usually relevant or related to what the teachers are teaching in class and as a result, they have an immediate impact on teacher performance. It is an active professional development programme, based in the classroom, reliable and supported by other teachers (Stewart, 2014). During these collaborations, teachers' own experiences and practical needs are taken into consideration as essential to the CPTD programme (Vangrieken, Meredith, Packer & Kyndt, 2017). As a result, teachers can provide learning on their own, without relying on external experts. For Darling-Hammond et al., (2017), collaboration must be between individual teachers, between small groups within the school, or between teachers from other schools, it could also be a collaboration with other professionals from outside the schooling system. According to Ntuli, (2012) the poor quality of the South African education system is caused by teachers' lack of commitment and capacity. Collaborative CPTD programmes can address both ills. Besides the approaches to CPTD programmes, it is important to briefly look at other factors which would affect the effectiveness of CPTD programmes to help improve the performance of teachers.

Factors affecting the effectiveness of CPTD programmes

Darling-Hammond, et al., (2017) define an effective CPTD programme as an organised, professional learning activity which results in the alteration of teacher practice that will lead to the improvement of learners' results. On the other hand, Saunders (2014) warned that since teachers work in different environments, one cannot make

a conclusive list of elements for effective CPTD programmes, but rather consider an assortment of basic elements which make the programmes more effective. Some of these factors include;

Application of adult learning principles

Teachers are adults and, therefore, it becomes imperative that when teaching them, adult learning principles are applied. Saunders (2014) suggests that for CPTD programmes to be effective, they should be based on adult learning principles. These principles are drawn from adult learning theories based on adults' personalities, needs, and learning styles.

Specialist support

Steyn (2009) emphasises that specialists, in addition to **their content knowledge**, must have a good understanding of what is happening at the ground level, so that they can easily relate to the problems faced by teachers. The specialists need to model the new approaches, show powerful strategies, give support through their observations and discussions, and gradually let teachers own the strategies.

Mentoring and coaching

Lofthouse, Leat, Towler, Hall & Cummings (2010) suggested that the mentor must engage in a sustained professional dialogue with the mentee, which focuses on developing specific skills to enhance their teaching. Teacher coaching is regarded as a key lever for improving the teachers' classroom instruction and for translating knowledge into new classroom practices (Kraft, Blazer & Hogan, 2017).

Learners and teachers need

Darling-Hammond, et.al., (2017) asserts that to be relevant and effective, the content of the CPTD programmes must be informed by the objectives and aims set by the schools, taking into consideration the various learner and teacher populations.

Duration of the CPTD programmes

CPTD programmes must be seen as a process, not as a once-off event (Bautista & Ortega-Ruiz, 2015). Continuous engagement of teachers in CPTD programmes enables them to discuss and debate the programmes and related issues.

Structured groups

To ensure the effectiveness of the CPTD programmes, teachers have to work in groups to share information and experiences amongst themselves (Lantz-Andersson, Lundin, & Selwyn, 2018). It also enables networking and discussions of matters of common interest.

Support by management

School leaders must identify the professional needs of their teachers and arrange appropriate training sessions to meet those needs (Liu, Tsai & Huang, 2015). Jones (2018) adds that leadership plays a significant role in creating and sustaining a productive culture of professional learning within an institution.

Subject matter-specific

Bautista & Ortega-Ruiz (2015) emphasise that CPTD programmes have to be subject matter specific so that they provide teachers with a better understanding of the subject matter and pedagogical strategies to teach that content to learners.

Monitoring and evaluation

Saunders (2014) asserts that good systems must be created to track CPTD programmes, which will analyse the quality and impact of CPTD programmes. Monitoring can help facilitators detect flaws in the CPTD programmes (Desimone and Garet, 2015), and it can also help in understanding other activities which can make the programmes more effective.

Modelling

Gulamhussein (2013) states that many scholars agree that modelling is very successful in helping teachers understand and apply new strategies. One of the major factors which inspire teachers to change their classroom practices is when mentors and facilitators model new teaching practices, as they encourage teachers to implement them.

The environment in which schools are located

Qablan (2015) contends that the weak participation of teachers in CPTD programmes is caused by several discouraging contextual factors. Rural schools in South Africa still bear the disparities of the past, which makes it difficult to implement CPTD programmes.

Theoretical Framework

This paper is underpinned by the Andragogy theory which is an adult learning theory. This theory is directly related to CPTD programmes because teachers are adults. Seyoum & Basha (2017). Jones (2018) maintains that research has established that teachers' motivation to learn is based on the following structures: teacher education or professional development, educational psychology, educational policy, and andragogy. Furthermore,

Suwithida(2018) conducted a comparative study amongst the most popular adult learning theories and found that andragogy is the most wide-ranging theory of adult learning. The same sentiment is held by Sato, Haegele & Foot (2017) when they state that when delivering a learning programme directed at working professionals or other adult learners, andragogy is the most useful framework. The theory of andragogy was made popular by an American Malcolm Knowles (1913-1997) who developed its central doctrines based on the original theories of Eduard Linderman and other scholars (Knowles 1973). The term andragogy is made up of two terms, andro meaning a man and agrougus meaning to lead (Sato, et al., 2017). The term means to lead a man, and in this instance, a man stands for an adult human. Andragogy is different from the term pedagogy where peda- means a child, and hence pedagogics is concerned with leading a child (Sato, et al., 2017). Andragogy theory focuses on improving adult life by providing skills and the ability to solve problems. It develops life-long learning by changing the way new concepts are gained. Tezcan (2022) recommends andragogy since it is the most efficient model of adult learning, and it improves the way the country's workforce is trained to be competent. The first serious construct of andragogy by Knowles (1980) was the suggestion that the main reason why adult education is failing to contribute to the development of humankind is that most teachers who teach adults teach them as if they were teaching children. But the way knowledge is transmitted (pedagogics) to adults makes it impossible for adults to cope with the evolution of knowledge in the present society (Knowles, 1980). They maintain that the difference between andragogy and pedagogy is not the capabilities of participants but the nature and purpose of the processes. In the pedagogic learning process, the focus is on helping the child to be a responsible adult. Whereas in andragogy, the aim is to help the adult towards actualisation and full development (Clardy, 2012). For these reasons, Ekoto & Gaikwad (2015) concluded that the basic principle of andragogy must be that adults and children have different learning mannerisms and characteristics and these differences affect the processes of both their programmes and learning activities. The Andragogy theory was designed to have elements which will guide the learning activities that occur before, during, and after the adult learning practice (Leigh, Whitted & Hamilton, 2015). It is a distinctive and coherent theory of learning to justify the treatment of adults as adults in the learning process. Hidayat (2018) views andragogy as a theory concerned with the development of adult life by providing adults with the skills and ability to solve problems experienced in the life of a society. In andragogy theory, the facilitator creates a learning environment which physically and psychologically respects adult learners and then includes these adults in the planning, delivery, and evaluation of their learning (Robinson, Wilson & Mcneill-Cook, 2017). Mutual respect between the learners and teachers and between learners themselves is a basic element in creating a safe learning environment. Sato et al. (2017) pose that instructors must design the project to meet the interests of adult learners by involving them in planning project aims and undertakings while solving real-world professional matters and problems. According to Maddalena (2015), andragogy theory is based on six assumptions, namely, the need to know why, the learners' self-concept, the role of experience, readiness to learn, orientation to learn and motivation to learn. Adults need to know why they must learn something before they involve themselves in the learning process; adults need to know what they are going to benefit from the programme (Rasmussen (2015). Self-directed learning is the most preferred among adult learners and ensures that the learning experiences involve linking new knowledge to the existing one. Furthermore, they want information which they will readily use in real situations and in their occupations. The main motivation for adults to learn is intrinsic motivation, which includes the need to improve the quality, efficiency, and effectiveness of the different aspects of their life (Tezcan, 2022). The andragogy theory with all its assumptions is well suited to provide a proper lens through which to look at the suitability of CPTD programmes provided by the Zululand District for the improvement of the teachers' performance.

Method

This study adopted a qualitative research design. This was because the study wanted to get the experience of the participants with CPTD programmes they were receiving from the Zululand district. According to Creswell (2014), if a researcher wants to know about the participants' feelings towards a phenomenon, the most appropriate research design is the qualitative design. The research paradigm which was employed in this study was the interpretive paradigm which embraces an inductive approach to research which starts with data and goes on to derive a theory from observed data. Therefore, the interpretative perspective is concerned with the understanding of day-to-day social interactions (Edward & Holland, 2013). The interpretative perspective favours the qualitative method of research because both are based on subjective meaning, and they are conducted in a natural setting. The interpretative perspective was relevant to this study because it was based on how the teachers interpreted and practised the implementation of CPTD programmes presented by the Zululand district. One-on-one interviews were conducted with one primary school principal, one secondary school principal and a district official. Focus group discussions were held with six members of the SMT from primary schools and six SMT members from secondary schools. Focus group interviews were also conducted with six PL1 teachers from primary schools and six PL1 teachers from secondary schools. In total, the study had a total population of 27 participants. Data was also collected by analysing all documents related to CPTD at schools and the Zululand district office. Cohen, Manion & Morrison (2018) state that there are two types of

documents: namely, primary, and secondary documents. The former includes documents produced during the process of the activity. In this study, primary documents included CPTD files, minutes of meetings for CPTD, and professional development portfolios for teachers. Secondary data includes documents CPTD implementation document of the DBE and management of CPTD, documents provided by SACE regarding the implementation and management of CPTD by teachers, and certificates awarded to teachers for participation. At the district, the records for the training of teachers served as both primary and secondary documents.

The analysis of data in the qualitative approach is an inductive process where data is organised into categories where patterns and relationships are identified (Byrne, 2022). After data has been collected from face-to-face interviews and focus group interviews. Data were audio recorded by the researchers with participants' approval and then transcribed word-for-word to facilitate the analysis process. Emerging themes which involved the classification and presentation of data patterns were analysed. Participants were assured that their participation is voluntary that they can withdraw at any time, and they would remain anonymous. The researcher did this to gain the trust and confidence of the participants so that they could easily provide the maximum amount of data related to the study without any fear or doubt of being victimised.

Findings

There were ten themes which emerged from the lived experiences and insights of the participants of the CPTD programmes which are provided by the Zululand District. To ensure the confidentiality and anonymity of participants, pseudonyms have been practised in the study.

Focus areas of the CPTD programmes

Most of the participants stated that programmes are focused on content knowledge. The CPTD programmes are meant to develop teachers professionally which means that all the areas which affect the teachers' performance must be targeted by the CPTD programmes.

This is evidenced by the following participants' responses.

"Whenever we are called for workshops, it is only for content knowledge and assessment. The advisors rarely talk about the different skills of teaching and the other problem areas we have as teachers. The only thing the subject advisors talk about in these workshops is what we are expected to teach". (PLP1)

"Every time we are called by the district it is only for subject content. In the past years, we did have workshops directed towards managerial skills, but these have since been done away with, as a result, our management skills are never sharpened, except maybe once a while where we are workshoped on curriculum management, even then we are just shown how to fill curriculum management tools". (SMTP1)

Some other participants suggested that CPTD programmes must also include management issues such as classroom management and the professional conduct of teachers.

"I would have liked it if the CPTD programmes would also be directed to areas like classroom management which has proven to be a major problem, especially with the newly appointed teacher. The other area which needs urgent attention by the district is the professional conduct of teachers". (PP)

Teachers needs

To be successful in their aim of professionally developing teachers, the planners of the CPTD programmes must, as a starting point, identify the needs of the teachers.

A participant suggested:

Data revealed that teachers need to be consulted about the areas of development they require from the department. Their responses are as follows:

"These programmes must be so structured that they address our needs because as adults we know which areas of our profession need development. The only thing which the department must do is to ask us about our needs". (SMTP1)

"Even though the programmes are mainly directed at curriculum delivery, it is the subject advisors who decide which areas need to be treated. Even for those areas, you find that the subject advisor does not give teachers enough time to prepare so that there can be proper engagements, as a result, the teachers just sit there listening and take notes". (SMTS 3)

"If teachers could be consulted about their needs, they will raise specific problem areas which they wish could be addressed. It is during these sessions that possible solutions to problem areas may be found. If these sessions can be properly planned, teachers and officials can deliberate on these problematic areas and come up with possible solutions". (SMTS 1)

"There must be nothing for us without us. Such an approach attracts resistance from teachers, who feel that they are coerced into the programme". (PS)

Integrated quality management system (IQMS)

One of the very important aims of IQMS is the identification of the teachers' professional needs so that their performance may be enhanced.

A participant observed:

“Schools do submit their school improvement plans to the district, but a large number of schools in the Zululand district makes it impossible even to start working on them. It would be better if circuits could first develop their programmes. I must admit we do not use school improvement plans to develop CPTD programmes for the district or the district development plan”. (ZDS)

One participant explained:

“At the beginning of every school year, the Zululand District gives schools the district development plan and they are instructed to produce development plans which are aligned to the district plan. This takes away our right as schools to raise those problems which are peculiar to our schools”. (PS)

Data revealed that the district improvement plan is imposed upon schools. Therefore, a top-down approach makes it hard for teachers to own the district plan because they have not contributed anything to its development.

Duration of CPTD programmes.

One participant claimed:

“The CPTD programmes are held once a term for some subjects, some subjects have them once a year. It also does happen that some learning areas end up without a CPTD programme for the whole year. In some schools, I know some teachers have never attended a single CPTD programme for the past two years. With these gaps between the programmes, it is not easy to build on the knowledge which was gained from the previous meeting”. (PP)

Another participant added:

“Except for the meetings at the beginning of the year where the previous year’s results and the examiners’ reports are discussed, there is no time set aside for teachers to engage with advisors so that teachers and advisors can engage each other on problematic areas in curriculum delivery”. PLS

The district official confirmed that too limited several CPTD programmes are delivered due to financial and human resource constraints.

“The reasons we as a district offer a limited number of programmes and they have huge gaps in between is because of the shortage of both financial and human resources. The Zululand District is very wide in fact it is the largest district in the province in terms of size, the number of schools and learners. Another factor is the limit which has been placed on the number of kilometres the officials have to travel per month; they can only cover certain areas in that month.”. (ZDS)

A teacher also noted:

“Because our meetings have large gaps in-between you find that the facilitators will cram a lot of work in a short space of time. This results in teachers not being able to get the necessary clarification in terms of different concepts and the best ways of implementing the new concepts. The teachers at these meetings are not given time for feedback on the work previously done to check whether what they are doing is proper”. (PLS6)

The frequency and duration of the CPTD programmes are essential for effective and successful implantation. Data revealed that CPTD programmes are seldom delivered in certain subjects or learning areas.

Methods of CPTD programmes presentation

The effectiveness of a CPTD programme is determined by the models or methods used for presentation. Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) state that all successful presentation models provide teachers with opportunities to think about the programme, and to have input on that programme, it allows teachers to reflect, and make a change in the teacher's life. The effectiveness of the presentation methods determines how well the message carried by a particular CPTD programme will be delivered.

As for teaching models one participant stated:

“Whenever we are called for CPTD programmes the facilitators are always present in a workshop format. As a result, I do not know any other presentation models. This has become boring, because even if the knowledge is new if it is going to be presented similarly all the time it becomes monotonous”. (PLS4)

Another participant concurred:

“The method of presentation which is commonly used is the lecture method or a workshop, where the facilitators will distribute notes and give short explanations on some points and then tell us what is expected from us with little or no engagement”. (PLS6)

The method of workshop delivery was not welcomed by many participants because they claim it is ineffective in providing teachers with enough content, time, and activities for increasing teachers’ knowledge and in bringing about noticeable changes in the teachers’ classroom activities.

Efficiency of facilitators

A participant observed:

“There are instances where you find that the presenters are good, their presentations inspire you to look forward to the next session because the methods they use to present are inspiring and they can answer all

questions posed to them. But I must add that these are very few and mostly they are not from the Department of Education” (SMTP3)

One participant suggested ZD replied:

“If teachers are promoted to the district office, they must be made to attend special training programmes to equip them with the necessary skills to facilitate during the CPTD programmes”.

Participants highlighted the facilitators’ lack of content knowledge and which results in boring workshops. They emphasised the need for training facilitators so that they positively deliver on their mandate.

Time and location for CPTD programmes

A participant complained:

“The CPTD programmes presenters are given insufficient time to make presentations in the Zululand District. The CPTD programmes start at 12h00 and they must end at 14:30, because of the rural nature of our district it becomes impossible for teachers to get transport back to their schools after 14:30. As a result, the facilitators must use the quickest easiest and the same model of presentation”. (PLP3).

Another participant said:

“You have to wake up early in the morning to get public transport to the venue which is used for the programmes because you have no choice of transport means. By the time the programme starts your concentration is very low; you do not have the energy to lively participate in the activities of the programme. You are just there to get the notes distributed by the officials”. (PLP5)

On the issue of the district policy about time a participant, said:

“The only time we engage with facilitators and begin to learn like adults is when the established rule of the district is broken and we start our programmes at 9:00. During these programmes we learn a lot because we interact with presenters and other teachers. s”. (PPLS 3)

The Zululand District policy on CPTD programmes states that all CPTD programmes must commence at 12h00. This limits the time for CPTD programmes to two and a half hours which is not enough for proper engagements. Another problem is that most CPTD programmes are held away from their places of work.

Monitoring and evaluation of CPTD programmes

When the training has taken place, a system must monitor and evaluate the practices of the teachers to verify whether they are implementing what they have learned.

A participant lamented:

“When our teachers attend these programmes, we are not offered means and methods to check whether the programmes are implemented correctly in the classroom. You are forced to believe what the teacher tells you. As for me, I think every programme must have an assessment tool attached to it so that we can be able to supervise and check if the teachers are implementing what they have learnt at a particular CPTD programme”. (PP).

Another participant said:

“In very rare occasions you find that the facilitator will give teachers assessment forms which are used to assess the programme and the facilitator. But these forms are useless because we never get the results of those assessments” (PS).

Registration for the SACE-managed CPTD system

It was not explained to the teachers that the SACE-managed CPTD system was meant to encourage and recognise their participation in CPTD programmes. The teachers saw it as a burden which was increasing their workload. For teachers to participate in the SACE-managed CPTD system, they must register with the SACE management system. Most principals, deputy principals and some HODs claimed that they had registered. The problem was with post-level 1 teachers; all teachers in this group reported that they were not registered with SACE.

A participant said:

“Our principal just mentioned this SACE system when we were having a staff meeting. We all thought a follow-up meeting was still going to be held where a proper explanation of the system will be made. But this never happened, we were expecting the principal to take us through the whole process from registration to the end of the process” (PLP6)

A participant lamented:

“It was very much unfair for the district to expect that we could be able to train our teachers on the SACE-managed CPTD system when they had only trained us for a few hours”. (PS)

The management of SACE managed CPTD system

Asked about the PDP a participant responded by asking a question, which indicated that there is a gap in knowledge on CPTD programmes.

“Are we supposed to have another file besides the file we are keeping for our daily teaching activities? I have never heard of such a file”. (PLS3)

“We do not have a separate minute book for the CPTD programme. We discuss CPTD issues during our normal staff meetings. I am not able to check on teachers’ PDPs because we do not have PDPs in our school”. (PS)

Participants seemed confused when asked about their Professional Development Portfolios (PDPs). They asked several questions seeking clarity, as an indication of the poor implementation process.

Discussions

Research has shown that effective professional development programmes must have an element of continuity, active participation of participants, be related to the particular social set-up, be linked to what is happening in class and are connected to adult learning theories (Webster-Wright, 2017). The study established that all the CPTD programmes in the Zululand District were delivered using workshops and lectures. Bautista & Ortega-ruiiz (2015) state that when such methods of presentation are used, teachers become passive recipients of knowledge with no opportunity to collaborate with others. Darling-Hammond, et al., (2017) argues that workshops and lecture methods lack the necessary structures to give teachers responses and support. Similarly, Petrice & McGee (2012) maintain that these methods are too short, and they are not able to provide individual attention to the needs of the teachers. These types of learning by teachers usually take the form of a top-down approach where there is an expert who might misinterpret the information (Kempen & Steyn, 2016). In these methods, the presenter will determine every aspect of the programme, which will include what is to be learnt and how the learning will take place. When such an approach is utilised, teachers are not given time to interact with each other to interrogate the information. Avidov-Ungar (2016) states that one of the most important contributing factors which determine the success of the changes in an education system is the extent to which all concerned parties are included. This study found that these methods are based on the cascade model of learning where the district officials are trained, and they come and cascade the information to the teachers. The cascade method is very ineffective because by the time the information reaches the teachers, it is not as accurate as it was originally intended. Kempen & Steyn, (2016) state that some of the factors which make the cascade method not reliable include the facilitator's lack of proper facilitation skills, knowledge of training content and poor understanding of the context and application of training material. The cascade system is based on the principle that there is one expert who has all the information, and the participant must quietly listen to the expert while at the same time assimilating all the new information. This narrative presupposes that the teachers are ignorant and inexperienced (Bett, 2016). This is in direct contrast to the andragogy principles which state that when adult persons come to a learning situation, they bring along a lot of experience which must be considered when the learning situation is taking place (Knowles, 1980). The type of learning methods to which teachers in the Zululand District are subjected resembles traditional methods. They are very short, which does not give teachers time to assimilate the new information thus, they are less effective in attaining the anticipated aim. Research has shown that the most effective learning methods for teachers are modelling, observation, coaching and all models which encourage participation and provision of feedback (Cordingley et al., 2015). Nasreen & Odhiambo, (2018) argue that district officials must, always, grow their knowledge and skills of presentation to improve the performance of teachers continuously

During these learning sessions, there is no active participation of the teachers; teachers only take notes. Cordingley, Higgins, Greany & Buckler (2015) state that teachers must have a variety of learning activities so that they can approach the concept in a variety of methods. This enhances their understanding of the concept, and it improves their confidence in applying the new concept in class. Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) concur when they state that if teachers are actively involved in the learning process, it gives them time to directly engage with the CPTD programmes so that they can try out what they have learnt before they apply it in their classes. The study found that non-traditional methods, including professional learning communities, coaching, mentoring, and peer review are not practised in the Zululand District. The non-traditional methods have been proven to be the most effective methods of delivering CPTD programmes which can bring about development in the teachers' performance. Bantwini & Diko (2011) found that districts, particularly those in rural areas, fail to provide teachers with the necessary support to implement changes and developments. Bayer (2014) argues that the time taken by the CPTD programme is the determining factor in whether the programme is regarded as traditional or non-traditional. The programmes employed by the Zululand district have a short duration with no active teacher participation, hence, they hinder teacher collaboration, and are traditional. Patton, et al., (2015) maintain that effective CPTD programmes must be ongoing and sustained over time to increase the chances of teachers interacting and discussing the new knowledge and skills. The study found that in the Zululand District teachers' needs are not taken into consideration when preparing CPTD programmes. Teachers are self-directed learners who have a wealth of previous experience; they also have well-defined expectations when they engage in CPTD programmes (Knowles, 1980). Similarly, Louws, Meirink, van Veen & van Driel (2018) state that as a teacher grows in the profession, particular needs develop depending on the professional level at which the teacher finds himself, these needs can be addressed by specific programmes related to that professional level. The CPTD programmes can therefore be made effective when done collectively with the teachers where they will express their needs and how they want to reach those. Thus, SACE requires that district offices develop a district improvement plan which is informed by the needs of the teachers at schools. The study found that the Zululand district does have a district improvement plan, but it is not based on teachers' needs. Barahona (2018)

contends that the neglect of teachers' needs results in teachers not owning the CPTD programmes, exceedingly rigid programmes, programmes which impose one teaching strategy, and one-size-fits-all broad programmes which do not consider the different environments and teachers' personal needs. The success of a CPTD programme relies heavily on the skills of the facilitators who will be the implementing agents of the programme. In this study, it was established that all the officials from the Zululand District did not have any South African Qualifications Authority (SAQA) qualification for facilitation. The lack of facilitation skills is no surprise because all district officials are promoted from schools where they were practising pedagogic skills yet as facilitators, they need andragogic skills. Wynants & Dennis (2018) advised that facilitators must use a variety of methods of presentation with multiple means of engagement and various types of assessment to make learning interesting. It has been established that most of the CPTD programmes conducted by the Zululand district are content based. Even though the content is important, Rochintaniawati, Widodo & Herlina (2018) state that for a teacher the knowledge of the content is not enough; a teacher must have knowledge of teaching skills and methods of transferring that content to the learner. This is referred to as Pedagogic Content Knowledge (PCK). The South African government made it mandatory for teachers to participate in the SACE-managed CPTD management system (SACE, 2012), yet there are a lot of shortcomings in the implementation.

Conclusion

The study established that all the CPTD programmes in the Zululand District were delivered using workshops or lectures. These methods were too short, they did not address teachers' needs and, teachers were not given time to interact with each other and interrogate the different concepts. These types of learning usually took the form of a top-down approach where there was one expert who was dishing out information to the participants while they were expected to receive it without question. The study established that these approaches to learning originated from the cascade model used by the DBE, where the district-trained officials were expected to cascade the information to teachers. The problem with the cascade model is that by the time the information reached the intended audience, it was not as accurate as was initially intended; therefore, it made little change in the teachers' performance. These types of CPTD programmes were referred to as traditional methods. It has been discovered in this study that the CPTD programmes offered by the Zululand District were mainly focused on subject matter content.

Recommendations

The Zululand district office as an established agent of implementing all CPTD programmes must establish mechanisms to monitor how effective the CPTD programmes are administered before, during and after their implementation process. Teachers must be consulted when the CPTD policy and other policies of the district are drawn so that they can own and embrace it. This will heighten the involvement of the teachers in all the CPTD programmes. Teachers must also be consulted on the preferred method which could be used to deliver CPTD programmes; in this way, teachers become part of the whole process of implementing the CPTD programme. After officials have been appointed to the district office, they must be made to undergo training in facilitation so that they will be exposed to adult learning theories, especially the Andragogic theory. The district office should encourage schools to form PLCs that will help to make sure that what was learnt at a CPTD programme is successfully implemented at schools. This will help the schools to develop into learning environments; as a result, when a teacher has attended a CPTD programme it is not only that individual teacher who benefited. The Zululand district must have dedicated officials who will make sure that the CPTD-managed system is implemented. These officials will conduct rigorous campaigns to highlight the importance of SACE managed CPTD system. To make the campaign effective, the DBE needs to appoint agencies that are experienced in doing public awareness campaigns and make teachers aware of the SACE-managed system. Incentives in the form of certificates should be provided to teachers for taking part in the CPTD programmes. These certificates will serve as proof of the knowledge that a particular teacher has gained. These could be used by teachers when applying for promotional posts. These certificates will also serve as a source of inspiration for teachers to continue to engage in more CPTD programmes. Teacher unions will have to be much more involved in the provision of the CPTD programmes to their members. The unions and the district will have to collaborate to avoid a situation where there is duplication of CPTD programmes.

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